

**MEDIATION ROLE OF ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE
PERCEPTION OF ADMINISTRATORS' POLITICAL AND
PATERNALISTIC LEADERSHIP BEHAVIORS ON
CONFLICT RESOLUTION BEHAVIORS**

Mukadder Boydak Özan¹

Tuncay Yavuz Özdemir²

Zübeyde Yaraş³

¹Professor, Fırat University, Elazığ, Turkey

²Assistant Professor, Fırat University, Elazığ, Turkey

³PhD Student, Fırat University, Elazığ, Turkey

Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to examine the mediation role of organizational justice perception of administrators' political and paternalistic leadership behaviors on conflict resolution behaviors. The study was conducted with 330 high school teachers working in the central district area in Elazığ. Percentage, frequency, arithmetical mean, correlation analysis and hierarchal regression analysis was used in analyzing the data. According to the correlation analysis results, there are positive and significant relationships between administrators' paternalistic leadership behaviors and organizational justice perceptions and between political leadership behaviors and conflict resolution behaviors. It was observed that there are negative and low level significant relationships between paternalistic leadership and political leadership behaviors, paternalistic leadership behaviors and conflict resolution behaviors, political leadership behaviors and organizational justice. According to the hierarchal regression analysis results, organizational justice perception has a partly mediation role on administrators' political and paternalistic behaviors over conflict resolution behaviors.

Keywords: leadership, political leadership, paternalistic leadership, organizational justice, conflict resolution

¹ Correspondence: email zyaras@hotmail.com

1. Introduction

After putting forward that leadership behaviors expected from administrators varies according to their cultures and because each society has a unique culture, researches focused on the question concerning which leadership behaviors and approaches are expected from administrators.

While paternalistic leadership is expected in Asian and Middle East societies due to their cultural characteristics, it has been suggested that the paternalistic leadership style is less expected in the Western societies (Chen & Kao, 2009; Pellegrini & Scandura, 2006; Narrator: Cerit, 2009; Yardımcı, 2010). When these results are considered, it is possible to say that cultural difference reflects on the results of the study.

In the field of administration, paternalism is defined as organizing administrator-worker, master-apprentice or teacher-student relationships as superior-subordinate relationships (Oz & Kılıc, 2010). Farh and Cheng (2000) define paternalistic leadership as a leadership style, which morally guides individuals through a strict discipline and a paternal philanthropist approach. Individuals within an organization regard paternalistic leaders as factors that attach them to the organization (Yardımcı, 2010). In addition, unlike the duty and responsibility distribution in the traditional leadership approaches resulting from the superior-subordinate relationships, paternalistic leaders base the leadership process on a moral attachment resulting from the family atmosphere among the organization's workers (TanrıoĖen, Basturk & Baser, 2014). In organizations where the superior-subordinate relationships are based on paternalism due to the nature of this moral attachment, the superior bodies respond to the leader's concern and interest with sincerity and feeling of belonging (Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008; Yardımcı, 2010). However, leaders do not avoid their responsibilities as an administrator, do not make a concession of their authority and expect their rules and orders to be carried out (Yardımcı, 2010).

Political leaders state that it is crucial to become aware of the political truth and of the resolution paths for possible conflicts that can occur. At this point, knowing the shareholders and effectively managing conflicts are behaviors that are expected from leaders. Leaders cannot always fulfill group expectations; however, they create atmospheres for discussing and negotiating over differences that occur (TanrıoĖen, Basturk & Baser, 2014).

The term justice is an objective that people aim at in the social, political field and other areas of life (Chengi, 2009). Educational organizations, whose inputs and outputs are humans, are open systems with potentials to affect the society they belong in. Thus, the society gets affected when educational organizations achieve their goals.

Organizational justice refers to individuals' opinions on how lustful they are treated within the organization, to their perceptions about the distribution, operation, procedure and interaction within the organization and to the effects of administrator behaviors on organizational devotion and trust (Greenberg, 1990; Altinkurt & Yılmaz, 2010). Individuals set certain criteria in developing their perceptions about administrator behaviors and determine whether or not the administrators are fair based on these criteria. (Altinkurt & Yılmaz, 2010). Organizational justice promotes fair and moral practices to take place within the organization and focuses on to what extent the costs and benefits of individual and group activities are equally distributed to the individuals and groups (İscan & Naktiyok, 2004; İscan & Karabey, 2007).

When the literature on organizational justice is considered, there are three sub-dimensions of justice namely distributive, procedural and interactional (Egilmezkol, 2011; Gunes & Buluc, 2012). Distributive justice refers to worker perceptions about how equally the rewards, punishments and promotions are distributed among the workers within the organization (İscan & Naktiyok, 2004). The main purpose of distributive justice is to enable a perception in the individual that they equally benefit from the distributed resources (Ozdevecioglu, 2003). Procedural justice refers to carrying out a fair process or methods when making decisions about distributing the resources and rewards (Beugre, 2002; Nar, Ozmen, Arbak & Ozer, 2007). Interactional justice refers to workers becoming aware of justice through the communication between their administrators and workers (Ozdevecioglu, 2003). In interactional justice, the process is explained to the individuals by emphasizing moral principles (İçerli, 2010).

The differences among people and groups pave the way for conflicts (Schmidt and Tannebaum, 2000; Nar.: Samdan, 2008). Conflicts are inevitable once the behaviors of individuals or groups within an organization counter against the interests of other individuals or groups or when they set a barrier against their needs being satisfied (Gordon, 1997; Corey, 2002). Administrators undertake a key role in such events and their conflict management skills come to the forth.

Conflict can be defined as a drawback in satisfying social, psychological and physical needs of people and as a state of disagreement among people or groups (Peker & Ayturk, 2000; Eren, 2001). Conflicts are inevitable in the relationships among individuals and groups. Thus, it is better to focus on the benefits of the process rather than on the negative effects that conflicts can create (Bursalioğlu, 2000).

Previous studies have focused on the relationship between paternalistic leadership and job devotion, job satisfaction, motivation, organizational citizenship, organizational performance and job stress (Yetim & Yetim, 2006; Erben & Güneser, 2008; Cerit, 2009; Yeh, Chi & Chiou, 2008; Chu & Hung, 2009; Oz & Kılıc, 2010;

Yardımcı, 2010; Chou, 2012), its effects on the behaviors of individuals within the organization (Cheng, Chou, Wu, Huang & Farh, 2004), and the relationship between organizational justice (Koksal, 2011). There are also studies which examine the cultural dimension of paternalistic leadership and put forward its indirect relationship with organizational justice (Lind & Early, 1992; Paşa, Kabasakal & Bodur, 2001; Farh & Cheng, 2000). In addition to these studies, in the national and international literature, there are studies which underline that there are political leadership behaviors among the leadership styles of school principals (Messer, 2002; Dereli, 2003; Baker, 2008; Dias, 2009; Hall, 2010; Tanrıoĝen, Basturk & Baser, 2014); studies on organizational justice focus on its relationship with variables such as organizational citizenship, organizational justice in schools, the effects of organizational justice on teacher performance evaluations, organizational devotion (Hoy & Tarter, 2004; Comert, Demirtas & Ustuner, 2008; Annamalai, Abdullah & Alazidiyeen, 2010; Egilmezkol, 2011; Atalay, 2015); studies on organizational conflict are observed to focus primarily on conflict management (Ozmen, 1997; Sarpkaya, 2002; Mirzeoglu, 2005; Kandemir, 2006; Samdan, 2008; Erol, 2009). Previous studies have focused on the relationship between paternalistic or political leadership and certain variables such as motivation and commitment; however, there have been very few studies which underlined the relationships between organizational justice or conflict resolution behaviors.

2. Method

In this section, information about the sample group and inventories used in the study, which aims at determining the mediation role of organizational justice perception about administrators' political and paternalistic behaviors on conflict resolution behaviors, will be given. A factor analysis was conducted for each variable and the correlation coefficients regarding each variable were determined. Hierarchical regression analyses and Sobel tests were conducted to determine the effects of the independent variables on the dependent variables and then to determine the mediation role of organizational justice perception and conflict resolution behaviors, hypotheses of the study were defined by resorting to various studies and the findings were explained based on the analyses results.

2.1. The Study Group

The "simple random sampling method" was conducted in selecting the study group of the study. According to this method, each unit within the population has the equal and independent chance of being selected in the sample. In other words, each individual has

the equal the chance of being selected and neither participant affects the other individuals' possibility of being selected (Buyukozturk, Cakmak, Akgun, Karadeniz & Demirel, 2011:84).

Data were collected from a total of 330 high school teachers working in the central district of Elazığ during the 2014-2015 academic period. After examining the data 24 forms were filled in either incorrectly or incompletely, thus these 24 forms were marked as invalid and 306 scales were accepted. Demographic data concerning the teachers who participated in the study are given on Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Information Concerning the Teachers Participating in the Study

Type of School		Branch				Gender		Age	Seniority		
								(Ave)	(Ave)		
Anatolian H.	Vocational H.	Cultural Courses		Vocational Courses		Female					
f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
192	62.7	114	37.3	242	79.1	64	20.9	115	37.6	191	62.4
								39.03	15		

2.2. Measurement Instruments

Four inventories were used in the study as data collection instruments. Information on these inventories is given below:

A. Organizational Justice Inventory: The Organizational Justice Inventory, developed by Neihoff and Moormann (1993), consists of 20 items. This scale was translated into Turkish by Akgeyik (2014). The Organizational Justice Inventory, which consists of 20 items and which was translated into Turkish by Akgeyik (2014), was used in the study

The scale consists of three sub-dimensions, namely interactional, distributive and procedural justice. In this five point Likert type scale, five options were placed beside each question to express the frequency of each behavior. These options were degreeed as "I totally disagree", "I disagree", "I'm not sure (I partly agree/partly disagree)", "I agree" and "I totally agree" (1-5).

According to the explanatory factor analysis results, the scale was appropriate for a three factor structure and the factor loads were observed to be between .85 and .50. There were no items with factor load value below .30. Keiser-Meyer- Olkin (KMO) analysis result for the scale was .925 and the Barlett test was observed to be significant (p=.001).

B. Paternalistic Leadership Inventory: This inventory, developed by Pellegrini and Scandura (2006), consists of 18 items. This scale was translated into Turkish by Yardımçı

(2010). The Paternalistic Leadership Inventory, which consists of 18 items and which was translated into Turkish by Yıldırım (2010), was used in the study. The scale was developed with a five point Likert type degree and five options were given for each question to express the frequency of each behavior. The Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient for the study conducted by Yıldırım (2010) was .914, however, this value was .883 for this study. These values indicate that the scale has internal reliability.

According to the explanatory factor analysis results, the factor loads of the scale were between .81 and .51. There were no items with factor load value below .30. Keiser-Meyer- Olkin (KMO) analysis result for the scale was .886 and the Barlett test was observed to be significant ($p=.001$).

C. Political Leadership Inventory: There are 8 items concerning political leadership in the "Leadership Orientations Questionnaire"(LOQ) scale developed by Bolman and Deal (1991) to determine school administrators' leadership styles. The scale was translated into Turkish by Dereli (2003). The 8 items, concerning the political leadership dimension, of the Leadership Orientations Questionnaire scale that Dereli translated into Turkish were used in this study.

The scale was developed with a five point Likert type degree and five options were given for each question to express the frequency of each behavior. These were degreed as "never", "rarely", "sometimes", "often" and "always" (1-5). The Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient of the scale was .890 for this study. These values indicate that the scale has internal reliability.

According to the explanatory factor analysis results, the factor loads of the scale were between .83 and .60. There were no items with factor load value below .30. Keiser-Meyer- Olkin (KMO) analysis result for the scale was .892 and the Barlett test was observed to be significant ($p=.001$).

D. Organizational Justice Inventory: The Organizational Conflict Inventory was developed by Rahim (1983) and consists on 28 items. The scale was translated into Turkish by Gumuseli (1994). The Organizational Conflict Inventory, consisting of 28 items and which was translated into Turkish by Gumuseli (1994), was used in this study.

The scale was developed with a five point Likert type degree and five options were given for each question to express the frequency of each behavior. These were degreed as "very rare", "rare", "sometimes", "often" and "always" (1-5). The Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient for the study conducted by Gumuseli (1994) was .77, however, this value was .880 for this study. These values indicate that the scale has internal reliability.

According to the explanatory factor analysis results, the factor loads of the scale were between .85 and .47. There were no items with factor load value below .30. Keiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) analysis result for the scale was .915 and the Barlett test was observed to be significant ($p=.001$).

2.3. Data Analysis

The data were entered analyzed through a software program. Percentage and frequency values were used to express the demographic characteristics of the participants. A correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between paternalistic leadership behaviors and teachers' organizational justice perceptions and conflict resolution behaviors. The Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used in the correlation analysis. The lowest and highest value that the correlation coefficient can equal to was (-1) and (+1). However, in practice, (-1) and (+1) values are not always obtained (Baykul and Güzeller, 2014:578). In interpreting the correlation coefficients, values between 1.00-0.70 indicate high; values between 0.70-0.30 indicate moderate; values between 0.30-0.00 indicate a low level of relationship (Büyüköztürk et. al., 2011: 227).

2.4. Research Model and Hypotheses

In the research model, the purpose of this study was; to determine the effects of school administrators' paternalistic and political leadership behaviors on teachers' organizational justice perceptions and conflict resolution behaviors and to examine the mediation role of organizational justice perception in the relationship between administrators' paternalistic and political leadership behaviors and conflict resolution behaviors.

The following hypotheses were developed concerning the paternalistic leadership study and were tested.

Hypothesis 1: Administrators' paternalistic leadership behaviors positively and significantly affect teachers' organizational justice perceptions.

Hypothesis 2: Administrators' paternalistic leadership behaviors negatively and significantly affect teachers' conflict resolution behaviors.

Hypothesis 3: Organizational justice perception negatively and significantly affects conflict resolution behaviors.

Hypothesis 4: Organizational justice perception has a mediation role over the effects of administrators' paternalistic leadership behaviors on teachers' conflict resolution behaviors.

The research model created based on the hypotheses is given on Figure 1.

Figure 1: The research model

The following hypotheses were developed concerning the political leadership study and were tested:

Hypothesis 5: Administrators' political leadership behaviors negatively and significantly affect teachers' organizational justice perceptions.

Hypothesis 6: Administrators' political leadership behaviors positively and significantly affect teachers' conflict resolution behaviors.

Hypothesis 7: Organizational justice perception has a mediation role over the effects of administrators' political leadership behaviors on teachers' conflict resolution behaviors.

The research model created based on the hypotheses is given on Figure 2.

Figure 2: The research model

3. Findings and Comments

3.1. The Relationship between Political and Paternalistic Leadership Behaviors and Organizational Justice Perception and Conflict Resolution Behaviors

The correlation matrix indicating the relationship between political and paternalistic leadership behaviors and organizational justice perception and conflict resolution behaviors are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Average, Standard Deviation and Correlation Values concerning the Data

Variables	Ave.	sd.	A	1	2	3	B	C	D
A. Organizational Justice	3.26	.74	1	.65**	.86**	.92**	.70**	-.28**	-.45**
1. Distributive Justice	3.15	.81	.65**	1	.41**	.40**	.35**	-.16**	-.24**
2. Procedural Justice	3.17	.93	.86**	.41**	1	.74**	.58**	-.28**	-.42**
3. Interactional Justice	3.37	.89	.92**	.40**	.74**	1	.72**	-.25**	-.42**
B. Paternalistic Leadership	3.17	.63	.70**	.35**	.58**	.72**	1	-.30**	-.42**
C. Political Leadership	2.92	.80	-.28**	-.16**	-.28**	-.25**	-.30**	1	.66**
D. Conflict Resolution Behavior	2.97	.62	-.45**	-.24**	-.42**	-.42**	-.42**	.66**	1

*p< .05 ** p< .01, N=306

It is evident on Table 2 that there is a statistically significant relationship between paternalistic leadership behaviors and organizational justice perception ($r = .070$; $p < .01$).

It is suggested that teachers' perceptions on justice will increase positively as administrators' tendencies to display paternalistic behaviors increase.

It can be observed that there are negative and low level significant relationships between paternalistic leadership and political leadership behaviors ($r = -.30$; $p < .01$) and paternalistic leadership behaviors and conflict resolution behaviors ($r = -.42$; $p < .01$).

According to this finding, administrators avoid political leadership behaviors as their tendencies to display paternalistic leadership behaviors increase.

It is evident that there is a negative and low level relationship between political leadership behaviors and organizational justice ($r = -.28$; $p < .01$). A statistically significant positive relationship is evident between political leadership behaviors and conflict resolution behaviors ($r = .66$; $p < .01$).

While there is usually a positive and high level relationship between paternalistic leadership and organizational justice perception, the relationship between political leadership and conflict resolution behaviors is negative and at a low level.

While there is a positive and high level relationship between political leadership and conflict resolution behaviors, the relationship with organizational justice perception is negative and at a low level. There reason for this can be because administrators who display political leadership behaviors decrease conflicts by coming to an agreement and because they are competent in resolving conflicts.

3.2. Mediation Role of Organizational Justice Perception on the Effects of Political and Paternalistic Leadership Behaviors on Conflict Resolution Behaviors

A hierarchal regression analysis was conducted in order to determine the effects of administrators' political and paternalistic leadership behaviors on conflict resolution behaviors and to explain the mediation role of organizational justice perception on this

effect. When the mediation variable is included in the regression analysis with the independent variable, the regression coefficient of the independent variable (political and paternalistic leadership behaviors) over the dependent variable (conflict resolution behavior) decreases, the significant effect of the mediation variable (organizational justice perception) on the dependent variable (conflict resolution behavior) continues. Results of the hierarchal regression analysis, conducted to determine the mediation role of organizational justice perception, are given on Table 3.

With regards to the mediation test, the effects of the independent variable, political and paternalistic leadership behaviors, on organizational justice perception, whose mediation variable role was being observed, were examined.

Table 3: Results of the Hierarchal Regression Analysis Displaying the Mediation Role of Organizational Justice Perception between Paternalistic and Political Leadership Behaviors and Conflict Resolution Behaviors

Independent Variables	β	
	Organizational Justice	Conflict Resolution Behaviors
Test 1		
Paternalistic Leadership		-.42
		.182
		.180
	R=, 427 F=67,773 p= 0.000**	
Test 2		
Paternalistic Leadership	.70	
	.501	
	.500	
Paternalistic Leadership	R=, 708 F=305,761 p= 0.000**	
Test 3		
Paternalistic Leadership		-.21
Organizational Justice		-.29
		.226
		.221
	R= ,476 F=44,315 p= 0.000**	
<i>Sobel Test (z)= (z=4.06; p<.001)</i>		
Test 1		
Political Leadership		.66
		.437
Political Leadership		.435
	R= ,661 F=236,268 p= 0.000**	

Test 2

Political Leadership	-.28
	.084
	.081
R= ,289 F=27,771 p= 0.000**	

Test 3

Political Leadership	.57
Organizational Justice	-.28
	.511
	.507
R= ,715 F=158,070 p= 0.000**	
<i>Sobel Test (z)= (z=6.02; p<.001)</i>	

*p< .05 ** p< .01 *** p< .001

There are two independent variables in the study namely paternalistic and political leadership. In the first section, the relationship between the first independent variable, paternalistic leadership, and the dependent variable, conflict resolution behaviors was determined. According to the hierarchical regression analysis, paternalistic leadership, namely the first independent variable, negatively and significantly affects conflict resolution behaviors, namely the dependent variable ($\beta = -.42, p < .01$). In the second section, the effects of paternalistic leadership on organizational justice perception were determined. According to the analysis results, paternalistic leadership behaviors positively and significantly affect organizational justice perceptions ($\beta = .70, p < .01$). At this point, the effects of organizational justice perception, whose mediation role was being examined, on conflict resolution behaviors were reported ($\beta = -.45, p < .01$). Organizational justice perception negatively and significantly affects conflict resolution behaviors. In the third section, the independent variable paternalistic leadership and organizational justice perception, whose mediation role was being observed, were analyzed together and their effects on conflict resolution behaviors were determined. The effect of paternalistic leadership on conflict resolution behaviors continued even after being analyzed together with organizational justice, however, the coefficient value decreased ($\beta = -.21, p < .01$). The significant effect of organizational justice perception on conflict resolution behaviors continued ($\beta = -.29, p < .01$). After completing these processes, Sobel test was conducted to confirm the mediation role of organizational justice and this mediation effect was observed to be significant ($z=4.06; p<.001$). According to this result, organizational justice has a partial mediation role in the effects of paternalistic leadership on conflict resolution behaviors. Based on this result, it can

be concluded that Hypothesis 1, Hypothesis 2, Hypothesis 3 and Hypothesis 4 are supported.

Secondly, the relationship between the second independent variable, political leadership, and the dependent variable, conflict resolution behaviors, was determined. According to the hierarchical regression analysis, political leadership, namely the independent variable, positively and significantly affects conflict resolution behaviors, namely the dependent variable ($\beta = .66, p < .01$). In the second section, the effects of political leadership on organizational justice perception were determined. According to the analysis results, political leadership behaviors negatively and significantly affect organizational justice perceptions ($\beta = -.28, p < .01$). In the third section, the independent variable political leadership and organizational justice perception, whose mediation role was being observed, were analyzed together and their effects on conflict resolution behaviors were determined. The effect of political leadership on conflict resolution behaviors continued even after being analyzed together with organizational justice, however, the coefficient value decreased ($\beta = .57, p < .01$). The significant effect of organizational justice perception on conflict resolution behaviors continued ($\beta = -.28, p < .01$). After completing these processes, the Sobel test was conducted to confirm the mediation role of organizational justice and this mediation effect was observed to be significant ($z = 6.02; p < .001$). According to this result, organizational justice has a partial mediation role in the effects of political leadership on conflict resolution behaviors. It is evident that these results support Hypothesis 5, Hypothesis 6 and Hypothesis 7.

4. Conclusion and Discussion

According to the correlation analysis, conducted to determine the mediation role of organizational justice perceptions on administrators' political and paternalistic leadership behaviors over conflict resolution behaviors, there is a positive significant relationship between paternalistic leadership behaviors and organizational justice perception, a negative and low level relationship between paternalistic leadership and political leadership behaviors and between paternalistic leadership behaviors and conflict resolution behaviors. According to a study conducted by Koksall (2011), there is a positive and significant relationship between organizational justice and paternalism. The study conducted by Ayca and Kanungo (2000) suggests that employees expect their administrators to be paternalistic leaders. Other studies underlined that individuals have positive opinions about their administrators concerning the perception on organizational justice (Yazıcıoğlu & Topaloğlu, 2009; Altınkurt & Yılmaz, 2010). In addition, a study carried out by Akgeyik (2014) states that justice perception of teachers

is lower than those of their administrators. Studies have also suggested that paternalistic leadership, which requires administrators to be understanding, helpful and honest, can increase worker commitment, respect between the workers, job performance, commitment to work, motivation and decrease job stress (Yetim & Yetim, 2006; Erben & Guneser, 2008; Cerit, 2009; Yeh, Chi & Chiou, 2008; Chu & Hung, 2009; Oz & Kılıc, 2010; Yardımcı, 2010).

Study results indicate a negative and low level relationship between political leadership behaviors and organizational justice and a positive and significant relationship with conflict resolution behaviors. When previous studies are considered, it is evident that political leadership is one of the most preferred leadership styles among administrators (Messer, 2002; Dereli, 2003; Baker, 2008; Dia 2009; Hall, 2010; Tanrıoĝen, Basturk & Baser, 2014).

According to the hierarchal regression analysis, which was conducted to determine the effects of administrators' political and paternalistic leadership behaviors on conflict resolution behaviors and to explain the mediation role of organizational justice perception on this effect, the first independent variable paternalistic leadership has a negative and significant effect on the dependent variable conflict resolution behaviors and a positive and significant effect on the perception of organizational justice. It was also observed that organizational justice perception negatively and significantly affects conflict resolution behaviors. When the effects of paternalistic leadership and organizational justice perceptions on conflict resolution behaviors are considered, the effect of paternalistic leadership on conflict resolution behaviors continued even after being analyzed together with organizational justice, however, the coefficient value decreased. The significant effect of organizational justice perception on conflict resolution behaviors was observed to continue. Sobel test was conducted to confirm the mediation role of organizational justice and this mediation effect was observed to be significant. According to this result, organizational justice has a partial mediation role in the effects of paternalistic leadership on conflict resolution behaviors.

While the second independent variable, political leadership, positively and significantly affects the dependent variable, conflict resolution behaviors, it was observed to affect organizational justice perception negatively and significantly. The effect of political leadership on conflict resolution behaviors continued even after being analyzed together with organizational justice, however, the coefficient value of effect decreased. The significant effect of organizational justice perception on conflict resolution behaviors was observed to continue. Sobel test was conducted to confirm the mediation role of organizational justice and this mediation effect was observed to be

significant. According to this result, organizational justice has a partial mediation role in the effects of political leadership behaviors on conflict resolution behaviors.

References

1. Akgeyik, G. (2014). Anadolu liselerinde görevli yönetici ve öğretmenlerin örgütsel adalet algıları (Diyarbakır İli Örneği). Master Thesis, Dicle University, Diyarbakır.
2. Altinkurt, Y. & Yılmaz, K. (2010). Examining the relationship between management by values and organizational justice by secondary school teacher's perceptions. *Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 16 (4), 463-484.
3. Annamalai, T., Abdullah, A. G. K. and Alazidiyeen, N. J. (2010). The mediating effects of perceived organizational support on the relationships between organizational justice, trust and performance appraisal In Malaysian secondary schools. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, 13 (4), 623-632.
4. Atalay, İ. (2005). Organizational citizenship behavior and organizational justice. Master Thesis, Afyon Kocatepe University, Afyonkarahisar.
5. Aycan, Z. & Kanungo, R. N. (2000). Toplumsal kültürün kurumsal kültür ve insan kaynakları uygulamaları üzerine etkileri. Türkiye'de Yönetim, Liderlik Ve İnsan Kaynakları Uygulamaları. Ankara: Turk Psikologlar Derneği Yayınları.
6. Baker, B. (2008). Leadership orientation and effectiveness of chief student affairs officers on coalition of Christian colleges and universities campuses. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Indiana State University Terre Haute, Indiana.
7. Baykul, Y. & Guzeller, C.O. (2013). Sosyal Bilimler İçin İstatistik: SPSS Uygulamalı. Ankara: Pegem Akademi
8. Bolman, L. & Deal, T. E. (1991). Images of leadership. NCEL Occasional Paper No. 7, January, Nashville, TN: National Center for Educational Leadership.
9. Bursalıoğlu Z. (2000). Okul Yönetiminde Yeni Yapı ve Davranış, Ankara: PegemYayıncılık.
10. Buyukoztürk, S., Cakmak, E. K., Akgun, O, E., Karadeniz, S. & Demirel, F. (2011). Bilimsel Araştırma Yöntemleri. Ankara: Pegem Yayıncılık.
11. Chegini, M. G. (2009). The relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior. *American Journal of Economics and Business Administration*, 1 (2), 171-174.

12. Chen, H.Y. & Kao, H.S. (2009). Chinese paternalistic leadership and non-Chinese subordinates' psychological health. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 20 (12), 2533–2546.
13. Cheng, B.S., Chou, L.F., Wu, T.Y., Huang, M.P. & Farh, J.F. (2004). Paternalistic leadership and subordinate responses: establishing a leadership model in Chinese organizations. *Asian Journal of Social Psychology*, 7 (1), 89–117.
14. Chou, H. J. (2012). Effects of paternalistic leadership on job satisfaction-regulatory focus as the mediator. *International Journal of Organizational Innovation*, 4 (4), 62-85.
15. Chu, P. C. & Hung, C. C. (2009). The relationship of paternalistic leadership and organizational citizenship behavior: the mediating effect of upward communication. *Journal of Human Resource and Adult Learning*, 5 (2), 66-73.
16. Cerit, Y. (2012). The relationship between paternalistic leadership and satisfaction from administrator and work. *Ondokuz Mayıs University Journal of Education*, 31(2), 35-56.
17. Comert, M., Ozer, N., Demirtas, H. & Ustuner, M. (2008). The perceptions of organizational justice of secondary teachers. *Journal of Research in Education and Teaching*, 7 (13), 3-22.
18. Dereli, M. (2003). A survey research of leadership styles of elementary school principals. Master Thesis, Middle East Technical University, Ankara.
19. Dias, M. H. (2009). The leadership perspectives of former student government presidents and the post-college impact of the presidency. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, The George Washington University, USA
20. Egilmezkol, G. (2011). Organizational justice and organizational commitment in work life, a study aimed at the analysis of the organizational justice and organizational commitment of the employees in a public bank. Master thesis. Gazi University, Ankara.
21. Erben, G., S. & Guneser, A.B. (2008). The relationship between paternalist leadership and organizational commitment: investigating the role of climate regarding ethics. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 82, 955-968.
22. Erol, E. (2009). The statergres of primary school conflict management and how it affects the teachers stress levels. Master thesis. Usak University
23. Eren, E. (2001). Örgütsel Davranış ve Yönetim Psikolojisi. İstanbul: Beta Yayınları.
24. Farh, J. L. & Cheng, B. S. (2000). A cultural analysis of paternalistic leadership in Chinese organizations. In *Management and Organizations in the Chinese Context*, 85–127. London.

25. Gordon, J. (1998). The New Paternalism. *Forbes*, 162(10), 68-70.
26. Greenberg, J. (1990). Organizational justice: yesterday, today, and tomorrow. *Journal of Management*, 16(2), 399-432.
27. Gumuseli, A. İ. (1994). İzmir ortaöğretim okulları yöneticilerinin öğretmenler ile aralarındaki çatışmaları yönetme biçimleri. Phd Thesis. Ankara University, Ankara.
28. Gunes, M.A. & Buluc, M. (2012). The relationship between transformational leadership and organizational justice. *The Journal of Turkish Educational Sciences*, 10 (3), 411-437.
29. Hall, R. A. (2010). A quantitative study of differences in leadership frames of community college presidents of the baby boomer and generation x generations. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Capella University, USA
30. Hoy, W. K. & Tarter, C. J. (2004). Organizational justice in schools: no justice without trust. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 18 (4), 250-259.
31. Icerli, L. (2010). Organizational justice: A theoretical approach. *Journal of Entrepreneurship and Development*. 5(1), 67-88.
32. Iscan, O. M. & Naktiyok, A. (2004). Perceptions of employees about organizational commitment and justice as determinants of their organizational coherence. *The Journal of the Faculty of Political Sciences*, 59 (1), 182- 201.
33. Iscan, O. M. & Karabey, C. N. (2007). The relationship of organizational climate and perception of support for innovation. *Gaziantep University Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(2), 103-116.
34. Kandemir, A. (2006). Organizational conflict and compromise fields between administrators and teachers at high schools. Master Thesis. Abant İzzet Baysal University, Bolu.
35. Koksall, O. (2011). An empirical study towards determination of the relationship between paternalism and perceived organizational justice. *Cumhuriyet University Journal of Economics and Administrative Sciences*, 12(2), 159-170.
36. Lind, E. A., & Earley, P.C. (1992). Procedural justice and culture. *International Journal of Psychology*. 27, 227-242.
37. Messer, J. E. (2002). Elementary principal leadership orientations and selected professional and school variables. Unpublished doctoral dissertation. University of Central Florida, Orlando.
38. Mirzeoglu, N. (2005). Organizational conflict and management: A study at the schools of physical education and sport. Ankara University Faculty of Sport Sciences Spormetre *The Journal of Physical Education and Sport Sciences*, 3(2) 51-56.

39. Oz, E., Ü. & Kılıç, B. (2010). Paternalist liderliğin çalışanların iş tutumlarına etkisi. 18. Ulusal Yönetim ve Örgüt Kongresi Bildirileri, 20-22 Mayıs 2010, Adana: Çukurova Üniversitesi Basımevi: 681-688.
40. Ozdevecioglu, M. (2003). Algılanan örgütsel adaletin bireyler arası saldırgan davranışlar üzerindeki etkilerinin belirlenmesine yönelik bir araştırma. *Erciyes Üniversitesi İktisadi İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 21, 77-96.
41. Ozmen, F. (1997). Organizational conflicts and conflict management strategies at the universities of Fırat and Inonu. Phd Thesis. Fırat University, Elazığ.
42. Ozmen, O.N.T., Arbak, Y. & Ozer Sural, P. (2007). An inquiry about the effect of justice value on justice perception. *Ege Academic Review*, 7(1), 17-33.
43. Pasa Fikret S., Kabasakal, H. & Bodur, M. (2001). Society, organizations and leadership in Turkey. *Applied Psychology: An International Review*, 50(4), 559-589.
44. Peker, O. & Ayturk, N. (2000). Etkili Yönetim Becerileri. Ankara: Yargı Yayıncılık
45. Pellegrini, E. K. & Scandura, T. A. (2008). Paternalistic leadership: A review and agenda for future research. *Journal of Management*, 34 (3), 566-593.
46. Samdan, A.İ. (2008). Organizational conflict and resolution techniques: A survey. Master Thesis. Dumlupınar University, Kütahya.
47. Sarpkaya, R. (2002). Conflict management in educational organizations: a case study. *Educational Administration in Theory and Practice*, (31), 414-429.
48. Tanrıoğen, Z. M., Basturk, R. & Baser, M.U. (2014). Usage of four leadership frame model according to primary school manager's perception. *Journal of Research in Education and Teaching*, 3(1),348-358.
49. Yardımcı, C. (2010). Effects of paternalistic leadership behaviors on job satisfaction: an application on banking sector. Master Thesis. Hacettepe University, Ankara.
50. Yazıcıoğlu, İ. & Topaloğlu, I. G. (2009). The relationship between organizational justice and commitment: A case study in accommodation establishments. *Journal of Business*, 3-16.
51. Yeh, H.R., Chi, H.K. & Chiou, C.Y. (2008). The influences of paternalistic leadership, job stress, and organizational commitment on organizational performance: an empirical study of policemen in Taiwan. *The Journal of International Management Studies*, 3(2),85-91.
52. Yetim, N. & Yetim, U. (2006). The cultural orientations of entrepreneurs and employees satisfaction: the Turkish small and medium sized enterprises case. *Social Indicators Research*, 77(2), 257-28.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).